

Integrating Porter-Lawler Theory of Motivation and Hofstede's Dimensions of National Culture with Modelling Career Preferences of Graduating Students of Bangladesh: A Survey of Literature

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Abstract:- Selection of an appropriate career by graduating students, who are about to be included in the work force of any nation, whether as employees of any organization or as entrepreneurs, is of paramount importance for the students themselves, persons dependent on them, the organizations they will be working for as well as for the national economy as a whole. However, the preference for any career is dependent on demographic factors like gender, place of domicile, medium of education etc. as well as certain other internal factors like cognitive ability, psychomotor skills and emotional ability. Moreover there are external factors like industry position, state of national economy and its integration with the global economy. An important factor is the way in which he / she has been trained from childhood to perceive the suitability of different career options available to them. Another important factor affecting the career preference of graduating students is the level of motivation the student is having in the matter and the factors which determines such motivation. Moreover dimensions of national culture, as professed by Hofstede (2011), is also a moderating factor in this context. This paper aims doing an extensive survey of concerned literature and identifying the factors which have been found to be decisive on choice of careers of the students and then to propose a conceptual model of career preference by considering other factors which have hitherto not been considered.

Keywords:- Career preference, demographic factors, cognitive ability, psychomotor skills, emotional ability, motivation, conceptual model.

I. INTRODUCTION

Geciki (2002) defined career as an activity which can be occupational, commercial or industrial in nature pursued by an individual during his or her education life, after education or till the death. Redman & Wilkinson (2001) termed career as a process of application of one's cognitive ability, contribution to a profession over a long time and better building better business network. Emotional intelligence, adaptability, cognitive ability, and other core competencies have a significant positive influence on

graduate students' career preference and success (Amdurer et al. 2014). Career is simply understood as job or a group of jobs willingly done by an individual for a living and which is undertaken over a long period of time in the life of that individual. Hence, a decision regarding career, is decisive in nature which has a direct impact on the personality and economic status of that individual in future. In this dynamic economic and technological era, new entrants to the work force of any nation i.e. graduating students and entrepreneurs, face a dilemma caused by multiple sectors and their relative pros and cons. Career preference is thus a decision which is influenced by the concerned individual's perception and priorities. Career preference is thus a developmental process and extends through a person's life time. Career selection is one of the most crucial decisions made by potential incumbents i.e. fresh graduates. The career preferences of fresh graduates are particularly important because they are the potential new entrants in the work force of any nation, whether as employees of any organization or as entrepreneurs, and as such their decision will have a telling effect on themselves, their dependents and on the national economy as a whole.

In some countries, career preferences are largely influenced and controlled by the parental choices. Such decision is also considerably influenced by internal factors e.g. cognitive ability, emotional ability, interpersonal skills and psychomotor skills of the student and external factors like state of different industries in the national economy, the macro-economic situations and projections for the future and the integration of the national economy with the global economic scenario. Moreover the demographic aspects of the student i.e. gender, socio-economic status, national or international mobility, motivation and attitude etc., are also significant influencing factors for their career preferences. Scholars have observed that students have relatively higher preference towards career options which have higher employment potential as compared to others. However, such a common tendency rests on the access the students have to relevant database and the information search process adopted by the students. This study aims at gaining a deeper insight into about the career preferences of graduates across the globe. It also intends to identify the determinant

factors for such preferences and the relationship between such factors.

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objective of the paper is three-fold. Firstly, the paper envisages to study prior research work of scholars across the globe, to know about the factors which they have been mentioned to be the determining factors for career preferences of graduating students of different streams of education. Secondly the paper intends to identify the factors which have not been considered as factors in the prior research works. Thirdly the paper intends to propose a conceptual model of career preferences integrating the factors which have not been considered in the prior studies.

III. METHODOLOGY

As the first step, the study has considered the working definitions of two very important and relevant terminologies i.e. "career" and "career preference". Career, in this study, refers to the occupational, commercial or industrial activity, by which a person earns income. Career preference refers to free opportunity to select a desired or attractive career regardless of job market conditions.

The second step in the writing this paper has been to study the available literature on the topic of career preference of graduating students across the globe and to identify the factors identified by the scholars to be determinants of career preference by the students.

The third has been to study the factors which have not been considered in the prior studies but are relevant determinant factors for career preferences by graduating students. In this step, process-models of motivation and dimensions of national cultures have been studied to identify the theoretical causal relationships between these factors and career preference of graduating students.

The terminal step of this study is to propose a conceptual integrated model of career preference of graduating students envisaging the factors previously considered by scholars as well as models of motivation and dimensions of national cultures.

IV. FINDINGS

Gati and Asher (2001) compared pre-screening, in-depth exploration and choice (PIC model) in the context of career preferences among the students with the purpose to identify the role of PIC model in the student life while they choose career decision making. The study presented that the three-stage model i.e. pre-screening, in-depth exploration and choice (PIC) increases the quality of career decision-making process because PIC provides the framework that acts as most relevant when the individual is trying to decide which occupation to choose. **Swinhoe (1967)** researched factors affecting career choice among full-time students with commerce stream. The study showed that their self-interest and skill satisfaction, material rewards and status were predominating over the career preferences while the difference in social background and parents; education and

the students' attitude seemed to be connected with remarkable variations in selecting process. **Lichstein et al. (2009)** conducted the study on career decision making among undergraduate engineering students which revealed that students' perception regarding the profession strongly influences the career choices. The primary expectations from students were good salary to afford a luxurious lifestyle. **Sauermann and Roach (2012)** investigated the impact of encouragement as well as levels and changes on doctoral studies as a career preference. The findings supported the fact that students from science PhDs. were interested in academics but students from chemistry and physics preferred careers outside academia. The reasons cited for this discrepancy was number of available positions in the respected fields in academia. **Fizer (2013)** studied students in the context of agriculture and found out that students are most influenced by family while choosing a major discipline. Students also indicated that job opportunities, guidance counsellors, teachers, campus visits, friends were the most influential when selecting a major discipline. **Mao (2013)** dealt with student's choice in the field of finance and banking and found out that financial rewards was the most important motivator besides opinion of parents, siblings and other relatives. **Ozlen (2013)** focussed on university students which revealed that family, learning and technological environment in the context of career decision were most important. **Salami (2013)** found out that students, specially female students, considered environmental factors as an important determinant for a career preference. **Baloch and Shah (2014)** opined that family factors and social factors influence student's career decision-making process. **Pascual (2014)** found out that factors which affects career choice of students was his / her personality and ability. The study further revealed that there was no significant relationship between factors like parents' occupation, monthly income, peer factor etc and career choice by students. **Ahmed et al. (2017)** showed that the counselling sessions influenced the career choice of students. **Moltz (2017)** found out that preferences for public sector employment varied among individuals and across nations. Alignment with one's own values, goals and environment awareness were found out to be the most influential factors for a career choice. **Twumasi et al. (2018)** showed that job opportunity, job security, prestigious profession, high salaries, peer-influence, interaction with educators, parental support and family cohesion were the major factor which had an impact on career choice of students. **Castellanos (2018)** found out that campus climate, faculty support, academic involvement and encouragement played a major role in selecting the appropriate career by the students. **Dasan (2019)** showed that passion, workplace flexibility, role model and career decision-making self-efficacy were the most significant determinants for career choice of a student. **Islam and Islam (2013)** identified that streams of study were the most prominent determinant for career choice by students. **Chishty et al (2007)** comparative growth of particular sectors were the most sought after sectors by graduating students. **Tangem and Uddin (2014)** opined that company location, company size, flexible work schedule, service growth, job security, opportunity for international exposure, starting remuneration and benefits and company

reputation were the most important factors considered by students while choosing a suitable career. **Rahman (1987)** identified socio-economic condition, educational background and cultural orientations were prominent determinants of career choice by students. **Kabir et al. (2017)** found out that entrepreneurial education was a favourite choice among students. **Kumar (2017)** identified that female students were less as compared to their male counterparts who preferred accounting career. **Mostari and Roy (2018)** identified family influence, salary, flexible work benefits, retirement benefits, personal interest, job security played vital roles in career choice of students. **Saks & Ashforth (1998)** pointed out that students did not want to wait for a suitable career opportunity and took up jobs under pressure of time. **Abbasi and Sarwat (2014)** found out that job opportunities, family factor, role of higher educational institutions, influence of parents and teachers had significant effect on career choice. **Omar et al. (2015)** identified initial salary, working environment and employer reputation to be significant determinants for career choice of students. **Liang (2016)** identified perceived external prestige and image of the organization were important factors considered by students regarding choice of career. **Kazi and Akhlaq (2017)** found out that academic achievement, family, health factor, financial constraints, etc. played a crucial role in a student's choice of a career. **Wust and Simic (2017)** professed that cultural, socio-economic and political environments were significantly related to career preferences among students. **Abri et al. (2018)** found out that financial benefits was a crucial factor in choosing a career by students. **Dwivedi (2018)** showed that job profile, job security and growth opportunity were most important factors while selecting a job. **Rauff (2016)** found out that motivational level was an important factor for career choice by students. **Anand and Sankaran (2019)** opined that motivational factors, personnel growth, professional growth and personnel satisfaction were the most important decisive factors for career choice by individuals. **Alkheil (2016)** showed that five personality traits i.e. agreeableness, extraversion, openness, neuroticism & conscientiousness, had important influence on choice of career by a student. **Hossain & Siddique (2012)** showed that students consider their personal strengths and weaknesses most while selecting a career. **Kabir and Sajid (2014)** along with **Anake et al. (2017)** found out that interest in career, ability, aptitude and attitude to career, self-concept and perception, were important determinants for choice of career by students. **Ferry (2006)** showed that skills, life conditions and academic achievements played major roles in choosing the right career by students. **Ketter (2011)** identified graduates' emotional intelligence, communication skills and adaptation power to have direct influence on choice of their career. **Ahmed et al (2017)** explained how financial conditions of the family, social class, affordability and employability in a particular industry influenced the graduates to select their career. **Brown, (2002)** indicated family and friends play a significant role for graduates in selection of their career. **Brochert (2002)** observed that personality, environment and opportunity influenced students in making career choices. **Agarwala, (2008)** found out that cultural values, individual abilities, dominance of family members had greater impact on career preferences of

graduates. **Palos and Drobot (2010)** showed that family & financial position were important determinants of career choice. **Ajzen, (1991)** along with **Fouad et al. (2016)** found out that influence of family was the strongest factor in determining the career choice of a student. **Otwari et al. (2017)** found out that that students were influenced for choice of career by cultural values, personality, family background and national economy. **Mtemeri (2017)** identified family influence, gender, school environment and peer-factors to be significant contributors to a students' choice of career. **Veljkovic et al. (2019)** identified factors like family business history, personal abilities, preferences and tendencies to be important factors for choice of a career by students. **Fischer et al. (2006)** found out that gender, personality traits, career motivation and life goal aspirations had telling effects on a student's choice of a career. Role of gender in career choice by students was found to be a significant determinant by several authors e.g. **Sax (1994); Cable & Judges (1994); Browne (1997); Tolbert & Moen (1998); Konard et al (2000); Correll (2001); Jelinski et al. (2008); Behrend et al. (2007); Gadassi and Gati (2009); Khunou et al. (2012); Erb and Kansan (2015); Wesarat et al. (2016); Krishna et al. (2017); Verma and Bakshi (2017).** **Moy & Lee, (2002)** stated that career choice by graduating students was largely affected by the job attributes like job descriptions, work environment, compensation and security packages offered by the organizations. **Auken et al. (2006)** considered the individual's need for autonomy and independence as a motivating factor for selecting career in some jobs. **Birley & Westhead (1994)** considered social recognition and status as a motivating factor of individual's career preferences. **Schwab (1982)** identified pay, location, opportunity of advancement, match with student's personality, perception with organization's value & image were important factors in determining the career choice by a student. **Huang & Sverke, (2007)** explained how the graduating students considered their major academic orientation, gender, and personality to determine their career choice. **Fallows and Steven, (2000)** showed that factors like downsizing, rightsizing, horizontal structure of the organization also influenced career preferences of graduating students.

V. PROPOSED INTEGRATED MODEL OF CAREER PREFERENCE

A few of the prior studies done on the topic has identified motivation to be an important determinant of career choice for graduating students but no specific model of motivation has been identified in those studies. This paper argues that since a career choice is always based on expectations by students, the Porter Lawler Model of Motivation, which belongs to the Process Theories of Motivation, is an appropriate model to explain the choice of career by graduating students. This model is based on expectancy, which includes performance-outcome expectancy and effort-performance expectancy, instrumentality i.e. the combination of abilities, traits, and role perceptions, and valence i.e. preference for anticipated outcomes. Valence is represented by the value of reward i.e. returns students get out of a particular career. Expectancy is included in the perceived effort-reward probability and is

also related to perceived equitable rewards. This explains the choice of a student to go in for a particular job-profile vis-a-vis its pay-off. Instrumentality is the linking of effort to performance of the student, moderated by abilities and traits and role perceptions by such student. Successful performance then results in intrinsic rewards i.e. a feeling of accomplishment and extrinsic rewards e.g. increment in income.

Another important factor which is proposed to be included in the model is the national culture. Dimensions of national culture as postulated by Hofstede (2011), are six in number. They are (1) Power Distance, related to the different solutions to the basic problem of human inequality; (2) Uncertainty Avoidance, related to the level of stress in a society in the face of an unknown future; (3) Individualism

versus Collectivism, related to the integration of individuals into primary groups; (4) Masculinity versus Femininity, related to the division of emotional roles between women and men; (5) Long Term versus Short Term Orientation, related to the choice of focus for people's efforts: the future or the present and past and (6) Indulgence versus Restraint, related to the gratification versus control of basic human desires related to enjoying life. Each of these six factors influence the attitude of a student towards differentiated views on different career options available to him / her. The final choice of a particular career option results from this differentiated outlook. Thus, this paper postulates the following generic integrated model for career choice of graduating students which is contained in Figure 1.

Fig. 1: Conceptual Integrated Model of Career Preference by Graduating Students

The model proposed in this paper requires a careful composition of the constructs of the latent variables. This paper is expected to add to the existing literature on generic modelling of career preferences of graduating students as it suggests a more comprehensive and integrated model of career preferences envisaging the dimensions of national culture and Porter-Lawler model of motivation. The proposed model shall provide a deeper insight into career preferences of students which in turn shall contribute to the personal development of the students, level of entrepreneurship and economic development of nations and effective build-up of human capital in different countries. The efficacy of the proposed model needs to be tested empirically considering the mediating and moderating effects. The model needs to be tested in different countries across the globe to test the hypothesized causal relationship between the dimensions of national culture and career choices.

VI. CONCLUSION

Extant literature has precedence of upholding the importance of the effect of motivation on choice of career of graduating students but no specific theory of motivation has been identified in such literature. Moreover, dimensions of national culture however, as a determinant of career preference or choice by student, has not been considered in existing literature in the subject. As choice or preference is influenced by motivation and motivation is influenced by expectation, the theory of motivation by Porter-Lawler is appropriate as a significant determinant of career choice of motivation. Such choice is also influenced by the mental framework of the students which is built up considerably by the dimensions of culture of the nations the students belong to. Hence the Porter-Lawler theory of motivation and dimensions of national culture are proposed to be included among the determinants of choice of career by graduating students.

VII. SCOPE OF FURTHER RESEARCH

There exists a huge scope of testing and assessing the extent to which the Porter-Lawler theory of motivation and dimensions of national cultures are determinants of choice of career by graduating students. These two factors, as proposed in this study may also be tested and assessed as mediators and / or moderators for career preferences by students.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Abbasi, M.N. and Sarwat, N., 2014. Factors inducing career choice: Comparative study of five leading professions in Pakistan. *Pakistan Journal of Commerce and Social Sciences (PJCSS)*, vol. 8, no.3, pp.830-845.
- [2.] Ahmed, K.A., Sharif, N. and Ahmad, N., 2017. Factors influencing students' career choices: empirical evidence from business students. *Journal of Southeast Asian Research*, 2017, vol. 2017, no. 2017, pp.1-15.
- [3.] Akosah-Twumasi, P., Emeto, T.I., Lindsay, D., Tsey, K. and Malau-Aduli, B.S., 2018, July. A Systematic Review of Factors That Influence Youths Career Choices—the Role of Culture. *Journal In Frontiers in Education*, Vol. 3, no. n.d., pp. 58. Frontiers.
- [4.] Al-Abri, N. and Kooli, C., 2018. Factors affecting the career path choice of graduates: A case of Omani. *International journal of youth economy*, vol. 2 no.2, pp.105-117.
- [5.] Alkheilil, A.H., 2016. The relationship between personality traits and career choice: A case study of secondary school students. *International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development*, vol. 5, no.2, pp. 139- 152.
- [6.] Anake, P.M., Adigeb, P.A. and Bassey, P.O., 2017. The influence of personality traits on career decision among secondary school students in Yakurr local government area of cross river state, Nigeria. *European Journal of Alternative Education Studies*, Vol.2, no. 1, pp.139-141.
- [7.] Anand, R. and Sankaran, P.S., 2019. Factors influencing the career preferences of medical students and interns: a cross-sectional, questionnaire-based survey from India. *Journal of Educational Evaluation for Health Professions*, vol.16, no. 12., pp. n.d.
- [8.] Agarwala, T., 2008. Factors influencing career choice of management students in India. *Career Development International*, 13(4), pp.362-376.
- [9.] Ahmed, K.A., Sharif, N. and Ahmad, N., 2017. Factors influencing students' career choices: empirical evidence from business students. *Journal of Southeast Asian Research*, pp.1-15.
- [10.] Ajzen, I., 1991. The theory of planned behavior. *Organizational behavior and human decision processes*, 50(2), pp.179-211.
- [11.] Amdurer, E., Boyatzis, R.E., Saatcioglu, A., Smith, M.L. and Taylor, S.N., 2014. Long term impact of emotional, social and cognitive intelligence competencies and GMAT on career and life satisfaction and career success. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 5, p.1447.
- [12.] Baloch, R.A.S. and Shah, N., 2014. The significance of awareness about selection and recruitment processes in students' career decision making. *European Scientific Journal*, vol.10, no.14. pp. 536-552.
- [13.] Behrend, T.S., Thompson, L.F., Meade, A.W., Grayson, M.S. and Newton, D.A., 2007, April. Gender differences in career choice influences. In 22nd Annual Meeting of the Society for Industrial and Organizational Psychology, New York. Vol., no. n.d., pp.2-10.
- [14.] Krishna, Bharadwaja; M., Sharma, G.R.K., Harilal, R. and Suresh, J., career preferences of undergraduate veterinary students in Andhra Pradesh. *International Journal of Science, Environment and Technology*, Vol.6, no. 1, pp. 708-713.
- [15.] Buddeberg-Fischer, B., Klaghofer, R., Abel, T. and Buddeberg, C., 2006. Swiss residents' specialty choices—impact of gender, personality traits, career motivation and life goals. *BMC health services research*, vol.6, no.1, pp.1-9.
- [16.] Borchert, M., 2002. Career choice factors of high school students. pp.1-82. 2002
- [17.] Bandura, A., 1986. Social foundations of thought and action. *Englewood Cliffs, NJ, 1986*.

- [18.] Bandura, A., Barbaranelli, C., Caprara, G. V., & Pastorelli, C. 2001. Self-efficacy beliefs as shapers of children's aspirations and career trajectories. *Child development*, 72(1), 187-206.
- [19.] Birley, S. and Westhead, P., 1994. A taxonomy of business start-up reasons and their impact on firm growth and size. *Journal of business venturing*, 9(1), pp.7-31.
- [20.] Brown, D., 2002. The role of work and cultural values in occupational choice, satisfaction, and success: A theoretical statement. *Journal of counseling & development*, 80(1), pp.48-56.
- [21.] Browne, B.A., 1997. Gender and preferences for job attributes: A cross cultural comparison. *Sex Roles*, 37(1-2), pp.61-71.
- [22.] Bundy, P. and Norris, D., 1992. What accounting students consider important in the job selection process. *Journal of Applied Business Research*, 8(2), pp.1-6.
- [23.] Castellanos, M., 2018. Examining Latinas' STEM career decision-making process: A psycho socio cultural approach. *The Journal of Higher Education*, vol.89, no.4, pp.527-552.
- [24.] Correll, S.J., 2001. Gender and the career choice process: The role of biased self-assessments. *American journal of Sociology*, vol.106, no.6, pp.1691-1730.
- [25.] Cable, D.M. and Judge, T.A., 1994. Pay preferences and job search decisions: A person-organization fit perspective. *Personnel psychology*, 47(2), pp.317-348.
- [26.] Dasan, J., 2019. Recruiting Quality Academics: The Relationship of Passion, Role Model, Workplace Flexibility, and Career Decision-Making Self-Efficacy. *IJBE: International Journal of Business Economics*, vol.1, no.1, pp.20-37.
- [27.] Dwivedi, R. 2018. Analysing Job Preferences and Career Options: A Study Based on Student's Perspective, 7, pp. 1-16.
- [28.] Erb, T.O., 1983. Career preferences of early adolescents: Age and sex differences. *The Journal of Early Adolescence*, vol.3, no.4, pp.349-359.
- [29.] Verma, Esha; & Bakshi, Dr. Ritu (2017), Career preferences performance: gender based study.
- [30.] Fizer, D., 2013. *Factors Affecting Career Choices of College Students Enrolled in Agriculture*. A Research Paper Presented for the Master of Science in Agriculture and Natural Resources Degree. The University of Tennessee, Martin. December 2013. Vol., no., n.d., pp. 1-51.
- [31.] Fouad, N.A., Kim, S.Y., Ghosh, A., Chang, W.H. and Figueiredo, C., 2016. Family influence on career decision making: Validation in India and the United States. *Journal of Career Assessment*, vol.24, no.1, pp.197-212.
- [32.] Fallows, S. and Steven, C., 2000. Building employability skills into the higher education curriculum: a university-wide initiative. *Education+ training*, 42(2), pp.75-83.
- [33.] Ferry, N.M., 2006. Factors influencing career choices of adolescents and young adults in rural Pennsylvania. *Journal of Extension*, 44(3), pp.1-6.
- [34.] Gadassi, R. and Gati, I., 2009. The effect of gender stereotypes on explicit and implicit career preferences. *The Counseling Psychologist*, vol.37, no.6, pp.902-922.
- [35.] Gati, I. and Asher, I., 2001. Prescreening, in-depth exploration, and choice: From decision theory to career counseling practice. *The Career Development Quarterly*, vol.50, no.2, pp.140-157.
- [36.] Geçikli, F., 2002. BİREYSEL KARIYER PLANLAMA VE GELİŞTİRMEDE İMAJIN ROLÜ. *İstanbul Üniversitesi İletişim Fakültesi Dergisi | İstanbul University Faculty of Communication Journal*, (15).
- [37.] Hofstede, G. (2011). Dimensionalizing Cultures: The Hofstede Model in Context. Online Readings in Psychology and Culture, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.9707/2307-0919.1014>
- [38.] Hossain, M.E. and Siddique, T., 2015. Career Preference of Business Graduate in Bangladesh: A Case Study of Some Selected Private Universities. *Asian Business Review*, 1(2), pp.106-113.
- [39.] Huang, Q. and Sverke, M., 2007. Women's occupational career patterns over 27 years: Relations to family of origin, life careers, and wellness. *Journal of vocational behavior*, 70(2), pp.369-397.
- [40.] Islam, M.A. and Islam, M.S., 2013. Job Preference of Private Universities Students in Bangladesh (A Case Study of Some Selected Private Universities). *International Journal of Education Research and Technology*, Vol. 4., no.2, pp.77-84.
- [41.] Jelinski, M.D., Campbell, J.R., Naylor, J.M., Lawson, K.L. and Derksen, D., 2008. Factors affecting the career path choices of graduates at the Western College of Veterinary Medicine. *The Canadian Veterinary Journal*, vol. 49, no.2, pp.161-166.
- [42.] Kabir, S.M., Haque, A. and Sarwar, A., 2017. Factors Affecting the Intention to Become an Entrepreneur: A Study from Bangladeshi Business Graduates Perspective. *International Journal of Engineering and Information Systems*, Vol. 1, no. 6, pp. 10-19.
- [43.] Kabir, T., Sajib, M. and Hoque, R., 2014. *Do Personality Traits Influence Career Decisions in Bangladesh? - A Study on Undergraduate Business Students of Different Public and Private Universities*. *ASA University Review*, vol. 8, no.1, pp.110-127.
- [44.] Kazi, A.S. and Akhlaq, A., 2017. Factors Affecting Students' Career Choice. *Journal of Research & Reflections in Education (JRRE)*, 2, pp.187-196.
- [45.] Khunou, G., Pillay, R. and Nethononda, A., 2012. Social work is "women's work": An analysis of social work students' perceptions of gender as a career choice determinant. *The Social Work Practitioner-Researcher*, vol.24, no.1, pp.120-135.
- [46.] Kumar, T., 2017. Factors that influence Bangladeshi student's decisions to major accounting at the entrance of university. *Review of Integrative Business and Economics Research*, vol.6, no.2, pp.147-171.
- [47.] Ketter, P., 2011. Soft skills are must-haves in future workplace. *T&D*, 65(9), pp.10-10.
- [48.] Chisty, K. K.; G. Munir Uddin & S.K. Ghosh(2007). The Business Graduates Employability in Bangladesh:

- Dilemma and Expected Skills by Corporate World. *Brac University Journal*, Vol.IV, No:1. PP:1-8.
- [49.] Konrad, A.M., Ritchie Jr, J.E., Lieb, P. and Corrigan, E., 2000. Sex differences and similarities in job attribute preferences: a meta-analysis. *Psychological bulletin*, 126(4), p.593.
- [50.] Liang, Y., 2016. Career Decision Making among Young Generations in China (Doctoral dissertation, Kent State University). *Hospitality and tourism management*, pp.1-142.
- [51.] Lichtenstein, G., Loshbaugh, H.G., Claar, B., Chen, H.L., Jackson, K. and Sheppard, S.D., 2009. An engineering major does not (necessarily) an engineer make: Career decision making among undergraduate engineering majors. *Journal of Engineering Education*, vol. 98, no.3, pp.227-234.
- [52.] Rahman. M., 1987. *Career Preferences and Employment profile Among Graduating and Graduate MBAs of IBA, Dhaka University*. *Journal of Business Administration*, Vol. 13, No.2, p-143.
- [53.] Moy, J.W. and Lee, S.M., 2002. The career choice of business graduates: SMEs or MNCs? *Career Development International*, 7(6), pp.339-347.
- [54.] Mao, S., 2013. Students' Choice of a Business Major and Career: A Qualitative Case Study of Motivation to Study Finance and Banking, pp.8-139.
- [55.] Veljkovic, Mitrovic. S., Maric, M., Subotic, M., Dudic, B. and Greguš, M., 2019. Family Entrepreneurship and Personal Career Preferences as the Factors of Differences in the Development of Entrepreneurial Potential of Students. *Journal Sustainability*, vol.11,no.20, pp.2-23.
- [56.] Mostari and Roy, 2018. Millennial's career quest: A study on the career preference of Business in Bangladesh. *International Research Journal of engineering and Technology (IRJET)*, Vol. 5, no. 3, pp.1-12.
- [57.] Moltz, M.C., 2017. Preferences for Employment in the Government Workforce. pp. 1-215.
- [58.] Mtemeri, J., 2017. Factors influencing the choice of Career pathways among high school students In Midland province. pp.1-179.
- [59.] Omar, M.K., Zakaria, A., Ismail, S., Sin, J.S.L. and Selvakumar, V., 2015. Job selection preferences of accounting students in Malaysian private universities. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, vol.31, pp.91-100.
- [60.] Özlen, M.K. and Arnaut, D., 2013. Career decisions of university students. *Journal of Community Positive Practices*, vol.13, no.2, pp.92-107
- [61.] Paloş, R. and Drobot, L., 2010. The impact of family influence on the career choice of adolescents. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, vol.2, no.2, pp.3407-3411.
- [62.] Pascual, N.T., 2014. Factors affecting high school students' career preference: A basis for career planning program. *International Journal of Sciences: Basic and Applied Research*, vol.16, no.1, pp.1-14.
- [63.] Porter, L.W & Lawler, Edward.E. (1968). *Managerial Attitude and Performance*. Burr Ridge. IL:Irwin.
- [64.] Rauff, M., 2016. Achievement Motivation and Career Decision Making Among Youth. *The Explorer Islamabad: Journal of Social Sciences*, vol.2, no.2, pp.49-51.
- [65.] Redman, T.&Wilkinson, A., 2001. *Contemporary Human Resources Management*, NewYork: Financial Times ,Prentice Hall.
- [66.] Sax, L.J., 1994. Retaining tomorrow's scientists: Exploring the factors that keep male and female college students interested in science careers. *Journal of Women and Minorities in Science and Engineering*, 1(1).
- [67.] Saks, A.M. and Ashforth, B.E., 2002. Is job search related to employment quality? It all depends on the fit. *Journal of applied Psychology*, 87(4), p.646.
- [68.] Schwab, D.P., 1980. *Recruiting and organizational participation*. Graduate School of Business, University of Wisconsin-Madison.
- [69.] Sauermann, H. and Roach, M., 2012. Science PhD career preferences: levels, changes, and advisor encouragement. *journal. PloS one*, vol.7, no.5. pp. 1-9.
- [70.] Swinhoe, K., 1967. Factors affecting career choice among full-time students in a college of commerce. *The Vocational Aspect of Secondary and Further Education*, vol. 19,no.43, pp.139-154.
- [71.] Tolbert, P.S. and Moen, P., 1998. Men's and women's definitions of "good" jobs: Similarities and differences by age and across time. *Work and occupations*, 25(2), pp.168-194.
- [72.] Turban, D.B., Eyring, A.R. and Campion, J.E., 1993. Job attributes: Preferences compared with reasons given for accepting and rejecting job offers. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 66(1), pp.71-81.
- [73.] Tangem S., Uddin, M.I. 2014. An investigative study on factors causing job choice of business school students in private university in Bangladesh. *International journal of Engineering, Business and Enterprise Applications (IJEBA)*, vol, no., n.d., pp.35-39.
- [74.] Van Auken, H., Stephens, P., Fry, F.L. and Silva, J., 2006. Role model influences on entrepreneurial intentions: A comparison between USA and Mexico. *The International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*, 2(3), pp.325-336.
- [75.] Wesarat, P.O., Sharif, M.Y. and Majid, A.H.A., 2016. A Framework for Assessing Gender Influence on Career Choice of Undergraduate Students in Thailand. 2016.
- [76.] Wüst, K. and Šimić, M.L., 2017. students' career preferences: intercultural study of Croatian and German students. *Economics & Sociology*, vol.10, no.3, pp.136-152